

About Smarandache-Multiplicative Functions

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The main objective of this note is to introduce the notion of the S-multiplicative function and to give some simple properties concerning it. The name of S-multiplicative is short for Smarandache-multiplicative and reflects the main equation of the Smarandache function.

Definition 1. A function $f: \mathbb{N}^* \rightarrow \mathbb{N}^*$ is called S-multiplicative if :

$$(1) (a,b) = 1 \Rightarrow f(a * b) = \max \{ f(a), f(b) \}$$

The following functions are obviously S-multiplicative:

1. The constant function $f: \mathbb{N}^* \rightarrow \mathbb{N}^*$, $f(n) = 1$.
2. The Erdos function $f: \mathbb{N}^* \rightarrow \mathbb{N}^*$, $f(n) = \max \{ p \mid p \text{ is prime and } n:p \}$. [1].
3. The Smarandache function $S: \mathbb{N}^* \rightarrow \mathbb{N}$, $S(n) = \max \{ p \mid p! : n \}$. [3].

Certainly, many properties of multiplicative functions[2] can be translated for S-multiplicative functions. The main important property of this function is presented in the following.

Definition 2. If $f: \mathbb{N}^* \rightarrow \mathbb{N}$ is a function, then $\bar{f}: \mathbb{N}^* \rightarrow \mathbb{N}$ is defined by

$$\bar{f}(n) = \min \{ f(d) \mid n:d \}.$$

Theorem 1. If f is S-multiplicative function, then \bar{f} is S-multiplicative.

Proof. This proof is made using the following simple remark:

$$(2). (d|a*b \wedge (a,b)=1) \Rightarrow ((\exists d_1 | a)(\exists d_2 | b)(d_1, d_2) = 1 \wedge d = (d_1 * d_2))$$

If d_1 and d_2 satisfy (2), then $f(d_1 * d_2) = \max \{ f(d_1), f(d_2) \}$.

Let a, b be two natural numbers, such that $(a, b) = 1$. Therefore, we have

$$(3) \bar{f}(a * b) = \min_{d|a*b} f(d) = \min_{d_1|a, d_2|a} f(d_1 * d_2) = \min_{d_1|a} \min_{d_2|a} \max \{ f(d_1), f(d_2) \}.$$

Applying the distributing property of the max and min functions, equation (3) is transformed as follows:

$$\bar{f}(a*b) = \max \left\{ \min_{d_1|a} f(d_1), \min_{d_2|a} f(d_2) \right\} = \max \{ \bar{f}(a), \bar{f}(b) \}.$$

Therefore,

the function \bar{f} is S-multiplicative.

We believe that many other properties can be deduced for S-multiplicative functions. Therefore, it will be in our attention to further investigate these functions.

References

1. Erdos, P.: (1974) **Problems and Result in Combinatorial Number Theory**, Bordeaux.

2. Hardy, G. H. and Wright, E. M.:(1979) **An Introduction to Number Theory**, Clarendon Press, Oxford.
3. F. Smarandache:(1980) 'A Function in Number Theory', *Analele Univ. Timisoara*, XVIII.